

Identifying the Impact of Economic Crisis on Mental Illness in Italy: What Are the Socioeconomic Gradients?

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ABSTRACT

Background: The advent of the global economic crisis has prompted increasing research on the impact of economic and social shocks on mental health and suicidal behaviour. Conceptually, economic crisis can affect mental health through increased unemployment, indebtedness, insecurity and decreasing welfare support. As one of the countries that were hit most severely during the recent crisis, Italy presents an interesting case to investigate the mental health consequences of the recession. Although several studies analysed the issue in Greece, Spain, Portugal, the UK and the US, to our knowledge no Italian study has utilized patient- and small area- level hospital administrative data to identify the causal effect on a national scale.

Objectives: The primary objective of the study is to measure the impact of economic crisis on healthcare in Italy, specifically focusing on neighbourhood socioeconomic determinants of admissions with mental disorder and their length-of-stay. We are also interested in testing whether hospital service utilisation associated to mental disorders changes according to the level of deprivation in small areas.

Data and Method: We exploit an eleven-year (2006-2016) panel dataset of hospital discharge information, containing mental disorder patients' demographic characteristics, diagnosis, length-of-stay and information on the admitted hospital, as well as data on the local socioeconomic and labour market condition at the level of clusters with common economic structure. Panel fixed-effect of unemployment rate on severe mental illness admission per 100,000 inhabitants and average length-of-stay is used to account for time-invariant heterogeneity. In order to address the issue of potential endogeneity of unemployment rate, we control for the fiscal capacity and other economic factors of the small areas. Further, we create discrete deprivation groups and perform a geographical analysis for standardised utilisation ratio to observe potential deprivation gradients.

Preliminary Results and Discussion: Preliminary results showed that unemployment is associated with higher admission rate for severe mental illness hospitalization after controlling for population size, average age, gender composition and percentages of different civil status. We expect to find significant impact of change in unemployment rate on severe mental illness admission after controlling for additional economic factors, as well as persistent inequality of utilization across different deprivation groups. The results will contribute to the literature of spatio-temporal variation in the wider determinants of health and shed light on the groups that are most susceptible to the effects of the economic crisis.